

A Study of the Physicochemical Characteristics of Strontium Palmitate

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The infrared absorption spectrum confirms the ionic nature of strontium palmitate. The specific conductance, density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity for soap solutions in a solvent mixture of chloroform and propylene glycol (70 : 30, v/v) at 40° are found to increase with increasing soap concentration. The CMC (0.01 M) has been determined. The values of degree of dissociation for the solutions (0.17–0.42) suggest that the metal soap behaves as a weak electrolyte in solutions. The density results have been explained on the basis of Root's equation whereas equations of Einstein, Vand, Moulik and Jones-Dole have been found to be applicable to these soap solutions. The ultrasonic velocity measurements have been used to study the ion-solvent interactions and the results satisfactorily conform to the informations obtained from conductivity, density and viscosity measurements.

Recently, industrial importance of alkaline earth metal soaps has been realised¹. Both the method and the conditions of preparation of the metal soaps may influence the physicochemical properties of metal soap to a significant extent. The survey of literature indicates that strontium soaps are the least studied among the alkaline earth metal soaps. The present work deals with the physicochemical characteristics of strontium palmitate. The reason for choosing the present solvent mixture is the appreciable solubility of the metal soap.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectrum: The infrared spectral bands for palmitic acid and strontium palmitate are recorded in Table 1. The characteristic absorption bands of carboxyl group of fatty acid (2 650, 1 700, 930 and 550 cm⁻¹) are found completely absent in the

spectrum of strontium palmitate whereas the absorption maxima characteristic of the aliphatic portion of the acid remain essentially unchanged when palmitic acid is converted into the metal soap. The absence of carbonyl absorption bands near 1 700 cm⁻¹ and the appearance of two bands corresponding to the symmetric and asymmetric vibration of COO⁻ ion near 1 410 and 1 530 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of strontium palmitate indicate that there is a complete resonance in the two COO⁻ bonds of carboxylic group of the soap molecules and that the soap possesses ionic structure. The assigned frequencies are in agreement with ν_s COO⁻ and ν_{as} COO⁻ modes of carboxylate group near 1 450–1 400 and 1 600–1 520 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of caproates, caprylates and caprates of Ca, Sr, Ba, Zn, Ni, Co, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm and Th. The values of ν_s COO⁻ and ν_{as} COO⁻ have been reported² in the regions 1 450–1 300 and 1 610–1 510 cm⁻¹ for the stearates of Ca, Sr and Ba metal salts of mono- or dibasic organic acids and metal salts of phenylesteric acid, respectively.

Conductivity: The increase in specific conductance (k) with increasing soap concentration (C) (Fig. 1) may be ascribed to the ionisation of strontium palmitate into metal cations, and fatty acid anions, in dilute solutions and to the formation of micelles in concentrated solutions. The plot (Fig. 1) is characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration, which corresponds to the CMC (Table 2). The k - C plot (Fig. 1) when extrapolated to zero soap concentration gives specific conductivity of the solvent mixture (k_0) which is consistent with its experimental value (Table 2). The concave nature of the plot of molar conductance (μ) vs square root of C indicates that the soap behaves as a weak electrolyte in these solutions and the limiting molar conductance (μ_0) can not be obtained by extrapolation of the plot. The following expression³ has been used to determine

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) WITH ASSIGNMENT

Assignment	Palmitic acid	Palmitate
CH ₂ , C-H asym. stretch	2 960	2 980
CH ₂ , C-H asym. stretch	2 919	2 920
CH ₂ , C-H sym. stretch	2 850	2 850
CH stretch	2 650	—
C=O stretch	1 700	—
COO ⁻ , C=O asym. stretch	—	1 530
CH ₂ deform.	1 460	1 460
C=O stretch†	1 450	—
O-H in-plane deform.	—	—
CH ₂ (adjacent to COOH group)	1 410	—
COO ⁻ , C=O sym. stretch	—	1 410
Progressive bands	1 350–1 100	1 350–1 210
(CH ₂ twist and wag)	—	—
CH ₂ , C=O rocking	1 110	1 125
CH ₂ sym. deform.	—	1 390
CH out-of-plane deform.	930	—
CH ₂ rocking	720	725
COOH bending	680	—
COOH wagging	550	—

Fig. 1. Plots of specific conductivity (k), density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (v) as a function of concentration (C) of the solutions of strontium palmitate in the solvent-mixture of chloroform and propylene glycol (70 : 30, v/v) at 40°.

μ_0 and K ,

$$\mu^2 C^2 = \frac{K\mu_0^2}{4\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^2}{4}$$

The value of μ_0 (Table 2) evaluated from the plot of $\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$ has been used to calculate the values of degree of dissociation (Table 2) for dilute soap solutions which again indicates the weak electrolytic nature of the metal soap in these solutions. The values of dissociation constant (K) (Table 2), calculated from the expression, $K = 4C^2\alpha^2/(1-\alpha)$ derived for the dissociation equilibrium in Ostwalds manner, are found to vary between 2.7×10^{-5} and 3.9×10^{-5} .

However, the true equilibrium constant (K') for the soap solutions, when the activity coefficients of the ions are not equal to unity can be expressed as

$$K' = \frac{4C^2\alpha^2}{(1-\alpha)} \frac{f_+ f_-^2}{f_{\text{soap}}}$$

where, f_+ , f_- and f_{soap} are the activity coefficients of cations, anions and undissociated soap molecules.

When the ionic strength is not too high, f_{soap} may be taken as unity. Using Debye-Hückel limiting law, one obtains,

$$\log K = \log K' + A \sqrt{C\alpha}$$

The plot of $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{C\alpha}$ for dilute soap solutions is found to be linear. The intercept of this curve gives the value of K' (Table 2). The values of α and K' confirm the weak electrolytic nature of strontium palmitate in these solutions.

Density and viscosity: The density (ρ) of the solutions of strontium palmitate in a mixture of 70% chloroform and 30% propylene glycol (v/v) at 40° increases with increasing soap concentration (C) (Table 3). $\rho-C$ plot (Fig. 1) is characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at the CMC. The extrapolated value of density ($\rho-C$ plot) to zero soap concentration (ρ_0) is found to be in agreement with the experimental value of density for the solvent (Table 2). The density results have been explained in terms of Roots equation⁴. The higher value of constant A than B (Table 2) of the equation⁴ (below the CMC) suggests that the solute-

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS FROM CONDUCTIVITY, DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND ULTRASONIC VELOCITY MEASUREMENTS OF THE SOAP SOLUTIONS

Temp. = 40 ± 0.05°, solvent : chloroform-propylene glycol (70 : 30, v/v)

Parameter	Derived from	Values	
		Strontium palmitate	Strontium myristate*
CMC (mol dm ⁻³)	k vs C , ρ vs C , η vs C and v vs C	1.0×10^{-3}	1.2×10^{-3}
k_0 (Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹)	k vs C	2.0×10^{-6} (2.1×10^{-6}) ^a	1.9×10^{-6} (2.1×10^{-6}) ^a
μ_0 (Ω^{-1} cm ²)	$\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$	1.01	1.33
α (below the CMC)	μ/μ_0	0.17–0.42	0.26–0.44
K	$(4 C^2 \alpha^2)/(1-\alpha)$	($2.7-3.9$) $\times 10^{-5}$	($1.3-3.7$) $\times 10^{-5}$
K'	$\log K$ vs $\sqrt{C\alpha}$	1.6×10^{-6}	2.5×10^{-6}
ρ_0 (g ml ⁻¹)	ρ vs C	1.0630 (1.0660) ^a	1.0666 (1.0660) ^a
Constants of roots equation	A B	2.4 -15.6	1.60 -7.8
η_0 (cp)	η vs C	2.02 (2.12) ^a	2.20 (2.12) ^a
\bar{V} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	Einstein's plot Vand's plot	10.0 12.8	11.0 12.8
Constants of Moulik's equation	M K	1.08 0.1×10^5	1.10 0.8×10^5
Constants of Jones-Dole's equation	A B	0.5 20.0	0.20 21.0
V_0 (cm s ⁻¹)	V vs C	0.994×10^5 (0.995×10^5) ^a	0.993×10^5 (0.995×10^5) ^a
Constants of Bachems equation	A B	2.0×10^{11} - 16.7×10^{11}	2.1×10^{11} - 7.2×10^{11}
β (cm ³ dyne ⁻¹)	$(\beta - \beta_0)/C$ vs $C^{1/2}$	9.5×10^{-11}	9.5×10^{-11}
ϕ_k^0 (cm ³ dyne ⁻¹)	ϕ_k vs C	- 6.3×10^{-7}	- 3.6×10^{-7}
ϕ_v^0 (ml mol ⁻¹)	ϕ_v vs C	- 0.90×10^{-3}	- 0.57×10^{-3}

*Ref. 13.

^aThe data in the parentheses refer to the experimental values for the solvent mixture.

solvent interaction is dominant over the solute-solute interaction, i.e. the aggregation of the soap molecules begins at the CMC.

TABLE 3—DENSITY AND VISCOSITY OF STRONTIUM PALMITATE IN SOLVENT MIXTURE

Temp. = 40 ± 0.05°, solvent : chloroform-propylene glycol (70 : 30, v/v)

$10^3 C$ mol dm ⁻³	ρ g dm ⁻³	$\eta_{c.p.}$	$10^3 \eta_{sp}$	η_{sp}/C	$(\eta/\eta_0)^2$	$1/\log(\eta/\eta_0)$
40	1.085 3	3.232	60	15.0	2.56	4.89
30	1.083 8	3.010	49	16.3	2.22	5.77
25	1.082 5	2.868	42	16.8	2.01	8.56
20	1.081 3	2.767	37	18.5	1.88	7.32
15	1.080 2	2.666	32	21.3	1.72	8.29
10	1.078 4	2.545	26	26.0	1.56	9.96
5	1.073 8	2.323	15	30.0	1.32	16.47
4	1.071 5	2.242	11	27.5	1.23	22.07
3	1.070 5	2.182	8	26.7	1.18	29.90
2	1.068 5	2.141	6	30.0	1.12	39.52

The plots of viscosity (η) vs soap concentration C (Fig. 1) and specific viscosity (η_{sp}) vs C (Einstein's equation⁵) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at the CMC. The extrapolated value of viscosity ($\eta-C$ plot) to zero soap concentration (η_0) is found to be consistent with the experimental value of viscosity for the solvent (Table 2).

The viscosity data have been explained on the basis of the well known equations proposed by Einstein⁵, Vand⁶, Moulik⁷ and Jones-Dole⁸. The values of molar volume of the soap (Table 2) evaluated from the plots of Einstein (η_{sp} vs C) and Vand ($1/C$ vs $1/\log \eta/\eta_0$) are found to be in agreement. Moulik's constants, M and K (Table 2) have been evaluated from the linear plot of $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs C^2 below the CMC. For dilute soap solutions (below the CMC), the higher values of constant B than that of A of Jones-Dole plot ($\eta_{sp}/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$) signify that the solute-solvent interaction predominates in dilute solutions. The results of viscosity and density are thus found to be in accordance.

Ultrasonic velocity measurement: The various acoustic parameters, viz. adiabatic compressibility⁹ (β), intermolecular free length⁹ (L_f), specific acoustic impedance⁹ (Z), apparent molal compressibility⁹ (ϕ_k), apparent molar volume⁹ (ϕ_v), molar sound velocity⁹ (R) and solvation number¹⁰ (S_n), for the solutions of strontium palmitate in a solvent mixture of chloroform and propylene glycol (70 : 30, v/v) at 40° have been evaluated.

The ultrasonic velocity (v) of the soap solutions increases with increasing soap concentration (C) (Table 4). The variation of ultrasonic velocity with concentration (dv/dC) depends on the concentration

TABLE 4—ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF STRONTIUM PALMITATE IN SOLVENT MIXTURE

Temp. = 40 ± 0.05°, solvent : chloroform-propylene glycol (70 : 30, v/v)

10 ³ C mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁻⁸ v cm s ⁻¹	10 ¹¹ β cm ³ dyne ⁻¹	10 ⁸ L _t Å	10 ⁻⁴ Z (cgs unit)	10 ⁷ - φ _k cm ² dyne ⁻¹	φ _v dm ³ mol ⁻¹	10 ⁻² R cm s ⁻¹	S _n
40	1.004 0	9.14	11.70	10.89	0.75	55.5	253.4	12
30	1.002 5	9.18	11.73	10.86	1.00	48.5	253.4	14
25	1.001 5	9.21	11.75	10.84	1.23	111.0	253.4	15
20	1.001 0	9.22	11.75	10.82	1.45	209.5	253.3	18
15	1.000 0	9.24	11.77	10.80	1.92	397.9	253.3	22
10	0.999 5	9.28	11.80	10.78	2.58	655.1	253.3	27
5	0.996 8	9.37	11.85	10.70	3.06	965.2	253.2	30
4	0.996 5	9.39	11.87	10.68	2.95	780.8	253.2	31
3	0.995 8	9.42	11.88	10.66	2.21	899.1	253.2	27
2	0.995 5	9.44	11.90	10.63	2.50	654.5	253.2	27

derivative of density (ρ) and adiabatic compressibility (β) as

$$\frac{dv}{dC} = -\frac{v}{2} [1/\rho (d\rho/dC) + 1/\beta (d\beta/dC)]$$

The derivatives dρ/dC and dβ/dC are opposite in sign with the latter negative and numerically larger than the former. Thus the velocity usually increases with increasing soap concentration. The v-C plot (Fig. 1) is characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at 0.01 M. The extrapolated value of ultrasonic velocity to zero soap concentration (v₀) is found to be consistent with the experimental value of ultrasonic velocity for the solvent (Table 2).

The decreasing adiabatic compressibility (β) with increasing soap concentration (Table 4) signifies that the internal pressure for the concentrated solutions is higher, i.e. the solutions become harder to compress¹¹. The adiabatic compressibility is found to obey Bachem's equation¹², β = β₀ + AC + BC^{3/2}, where A, B are constants and β, β₀ have their usual meanings. The values of A, B and β₀ (Table 2) have been evaluated from (β - β₀)/C vs C^{1/2} plot below the CMC.

The decrease in intermolecular free length (L_t) and increase in specific acoustic impedance (Z) with increasing soap concentration (Table 4) can be explained on the basis of lyophobic interaction between soap and solvent molecules, which increases the intermolecular distance leaving relatively wider gaps between the molecules and thus becoming the main cause of obstruction to the propagation of ultrasound waves. The molar sound velocity (R) increases whereas the solvation number (S_n) decreases at first (below the CMC) and then increases (above the CMC) with increasing soap concentration (Table 4). The solvation numbers are an indication more of electrostriction effects of the ions on surrounding solvent molecules than of the actual primary solvation numbers. The apparent molal compressibility (φ_k) and apparent molal volume (φ_v) for the soap solutions (Table 4) are found to vary linearly below the CMC. Their values for the solvent, φ_k⁰ and φ_v⁰ (Table 2) have been evaluated by extrapolating the plots of φ_k vs

C and φ_v vs C respectively, to zero soap concentration.

In conclusion, the present study on physico-chemical characterisation of strontium palmitate reveals several important facts which might be useful in deciding the applied worth of the metal soap. The infrared spectrum supports the ionic nature of the compound. The conductance measurements have been used to determine the CMC, electrolytic behaviour, degree of dissociation and dissociation constant of the soap solutions. The aggregation of soap molecules results in an increase in density and viscosity which vary widely with the nature of solute and solvent. The results of both density and viscosity are consistent in underlining the fact that the solute-solvent interactions predominate in these solutions. The ultrasonic measurements furnish added information on ion-solvent interactions and micellar behaviour of these solutions. The knowledge of the change in the values of various acoustic parameters, such as ultrasonic velocity, compressibility, intermolecular free length and solvation number etc., brought about by the addition of soap to solvent, provide information concerning the structure of these electrolytic solutions. For comparison, the important parameters derived from conductivity, density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity measurements of the solutions of strontium palmitate and strontium myristate¹³ in a solvent mixture of chloroform and propylene glycol (70 : 30, v/v) at 40% are recorded in Table 2. It may be observed that the results obtained for both the metal soaps are almost similar.

Experimental

Merck/AnalaR grade chemicals were used. Potassium palmitate was prepared by refluxing equivalent amounts of palmitic acid and potassium hydroxide in alcohol on a water-bath for 10-12 h. The soap was purified by recrystallisation from alcohol and then dried. Strontium palmitate was prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soap with a slight excess of the required amount of the solution of strontium chloride at 40-50° with stirring. The precipitated soap was filtered and washed with hot distilled water and

finally with alcohol. After initial drying in an air-oven the final drying was carried out under reduced pressure. Strontium soap was purified by recrystallisation and stored over calcium chloride. The purity of the compounds was tested by the elemental analysis.

For obtaining almost quantitative yields of the product (i) the solutions used for the preparation of metal carboxylates should be fairly dilute, (ii) addition of alkali metal carboxylate solution to that of metal salt should be slow and with constant stirring and (iii) the reaction mixture should be maintained at the proper temperature.

The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. A Toshniwal CL 01.10A conductivity with a dipping type conductivity cell with platinised electrode was used for measuring the conductance. Ostwald's type viscometer was used for measuring the viscosity (± 0.002) whereas density was measured (± 0.001) with a pycnometer. The ultrasonic velocity of the soap solutions was determined with single frequency ultrasonic interferometer (F-81, Mittal Enterprises) at a frequency of 1 MHz. The uncertainty of velocity measurements is 0.2%. All the measurements were carried out at a constant temperature ($40 \pm 0.05^\circ$).

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References

1. T. G. SOKOLOVA, YU. L. ISHCHUK, N. S. GOSHKO, V. A. PROKOPCHUK and V. V. SINITSYN, *Kolloid Zh.*, 1971, **33**, 895; A. BOUMAN, *Ind. Chim.*, 1950, **37**, 29; M. B. NAKONECHAYA, I. V. LEND'EL, N. V. SAMOILENKO and A. S. KRAVCHENKO, *Sb. Tr. Vses. Ob'edin. Neftekhim.*, 1973, **5**, 52; J. E. O. MAYNE and D. V. ROOYEN, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1954, **4**, 384; W. C. JOHNSON, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, **53**, 3733; A. J. LEHMAN, *Assoc. Food Drug Officials US Quart. Bull.*, 1951, **15**, 82; E. S. LOWER, *Ind. Perfum.*, 1947, **2**, 319; M. P. BESPYATOV and V. I. POLSTYANOV, *Maslov-Zh. Prom.*, 1932, **28**, 14; R. P. VERMA and P. BAHADUR, *Cellulose Chem. Technol.*, 1974, **8**, 189.
2. Y. KOGA and R. MATUURA, *Mem. Fac. Sci., Kyushu Univ., Ser. C, Chem.*, 1961, **4**, 1; C. DUVAL, I. LECOMTE and F. DOUVILLE, *Ann. Phys.*, 1942, **17**, 5; R. K. KAGARISE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 271.
3. K. N. MEHROTRA and A. KUMAR, *Colloid Polym. Sci.*, 1989, **267**, 80.
4. W. C. ROOTS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 850.
5. A. EINSTEIN, *Ann. Phys.*, 1906, **19**, 289; 1911, **34**, 591.
6. V. VAND, *J. Phys. Colloid Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 277.
7. S. P. MOULIK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4692.
8. G. JONES and M. DOLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
9. A. KUMAR, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 1990, **21**, 35.
10. A. KUMAR, *Acoustics Lett.*, 1988, **12**, 88.
11. S. PRAKASH, F. M. ICHIHAFOVIA and J. D. PANDEY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **58**, 3078.
12. C. BACHER, *Z. Phys.*, 1936, **101**, 541.
13. K. N. MEHROTRA, S. P. SHARMA and A. KUMAR, *Pol. J. Chem.*, communicated.